

Influence of Nebulizer Pressure Drop on Breathing Profiles and Aerosol Deposition in Human Airways

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Abstract

Breathing flow rate profiles are crucial for predicting aerosol drug delivery. While aerosol particle characteristics are determined by the inhalation device, breathing profiles are patient-specific, making them an essential topic for personalized medicine.

This study investigates the influence of nebulizer pressure drop on breathing profiles and subsequent aerosol deposition within human airways. Ten male subjects performed spontaneous and slow, deep breathing manoeuvres through three different nebulizers (one jet and two mesh nebulizers). Breathing profiles were recorded, and the impact of nebulizer pressure drop on flow rate profiles was analyzed. Computational modelling of airway aerosol deposition was performed for particles ranging from 1 to 10 μm in diameter, based on the recorded boundary conditions.

The jet nebulizer exhibited the most significant flow rate decrease due to its high pressure drop, increasing particle deposition in the lower airways. These findings are important for personalized modelling and the application of a digital twin approach in treatment design, leading to more effective and targeted drug delivery.

Keywords

Nebulizer, aerosol, breathing profile, inhalation, airways, deposition

27 **1 Introduction**

28 The future of pulmonary drug delivery and respiratory medicine appears to be firmly linked with
29 personalized and patient-specific approaches that employ digital twins and computational models ¹. The
30 boundary conditions for such computations must be derived from patient-specific data, including airway
31 images and geometries, FEV1, or cell, tissue, and organ levels ¹. However, if the treatment process
32 directly affects boundary conditions (such as inhalation behaviour), this effect must also be considered.
33 In addition to the aerosol particle size, which is a parameter determined solely by the
34 product/manufacturer, the inhalation flow rate and breathing profile are also crucial for pulmonary drug
35 delivery. The breathing flow rate profiles are patient-specific and can vary significantly due to
36 differences in lung volumes, disease stage, and other factors. The inhalation device also affects the
37 inhalation flow rate, particularly the devices with high flow resistance ²⁻⁴. Roth et al. ⁵ demonstrated the
38 impact of an air jet nebulizer on breathing patterns, revealing a significant influence on the inspiration-
39 expiration period, tidal volume, and shape of the breathing profile. Therefore, a personalized medicine
40 approach must consider the effect of the device on breathing to predict regional pulmonary deposition
41 accurately.

42 Nebulizers are devices for atomization and delivery of liquid medications. They are used for pre-hospital
43 as well as in-patient emergency care. The nebulizers available on the market can be divided into three
44 categories according to their technological principle: (1) jet nebulizers (JNs), (2) mesh nebulizers
45 (MNs), and (3) ultrasonic nebulizers (USNs). Jet nebulizers use compressed air driven through a nozzle
46 inside a channel with a liquid drug formulation. The formulation is drawn into the airstream by the
47 Venturi effect and atomized by shear forces. Jet nebulizers exhibit relatively low sensitivity to the
48 viscosity, surface tension, or osmolar variability ⁶. However, they are usually large and noisy non-
49 portable devices due to the necessity of compressed air. Moreover, the residual volume of the drug in
50 the reservoir is typically somewhat higher after the nebulization session (1 – 1.5 ml) compared to the
51 competing technologies. The drug delivery rate by jet nebulizer is also rather low, and the treatment
52 time is long ^{6,7}.

53 Mesh nebulizers contain a plate with numerous tiny orifices (mesh) connected to a piezo-electric
54 element, causing the plate to vibrate. The vibrating mesh tears the droplets from the liquid formulation,
55 resulting in the generation of an aerosol ⁶. These devices can be manufactured in portable versions
56 powered by batteries, and their operation is quiet. The small residual volume (0.1 – 1.2 ml) and high
57 delivery rate of mesh nebulizers lead to shorter treatment times than jet nebulizers. Additionally, the
58 droplet particle size can be controlled by the size of the orifices, which is determined by the
59 manufacturer. Thus, mesh nebulizers have become the preferred choice of nebulizer devices ⁷.

60 Ultrasonic nebulizers use piezo-electric elements to vibrate a liquid formulation container ⁶. The waves
61 generated on the liquid level result in droplet generation due to the high frequency of the vibrations ⁶.
62 The nebulization process in ultrasonic nebulizers is also quieter and faster compared to the jet nebulizer.
63 However, the most significant disadvantage of ultrasonic nebulizers is heating the liquid in the reservoir
64 during the nebulization process due to high-frequency vibrations. Such heating can be detrimental to
65 thermolabile drugs ⁶⁻⁸.

66 Nebulizers are an ideal option for patients who cannot adhere to the complex inhalation technique,
67 which is the most significant advantage of this technology, making it the only viable choice for treating
68 young children, infants, the elderly, or patients with severe stages of pulmonary disease. ^{6,9,10}. The
69 literature frequently assumes that the inhalation technique when using a nebulizer is normal spontaneous
70 breathing ^{6,11-16}. Different recommendations for nebulizer inhalation technique are mentioned in the
71 literature only rarely; for example, Zhao et al. ¹⁷ recommend holding the breath for 2 – 3 seconds after
72 a deep inhalation and subsequently slowly exhaling through the nose; or Arzu et al. ¹⁸ recommend to
73 breath normally with occasional deep breaths with JNs. However, the instruction manuals provided by

74 the manufacturer frequently recommend slow and deep inhalation during the nebulization session,
 75 probably to reach deeper lung areas by inhaling a larger volume of air or decreasing the flow rate to
 76 avoid droplet impaction. *Table 1* summarizes the instructions in the product manual for 12 standard
 77 nebulizers. According to *Table 1*, 50 % (6 devices) of the most common nebulizers require a slow
 78 inhalation and exhalation, while three mention “slow and deep” inhalation. The aerosol will certainly
 79 reach deeper airway regions when inhaled deeply. But will the slow inhalation decrease the inhalation
 80 flow rates significantly, and would it change the regional deposition? Following a specific inhalation
 81 technique (albeit very simple, such as “slow and deep” breathing) may introduce variability into
 82 breathing profiles and regional deposition due to individual patient adherence to given instructions.

83 Nebulizer devices represent a sort of flow resistance during inhalation, which may affect the breathing
 84 pattern. Roth et al.⁵ found that breathing through the air jet nebulizer differed from breathing without it
 85 in terms of tidal volume, time of inspiration and expiration, and cycle shape. These parameters
 86 significantly impacted the minute ventilation and thus the delivered dose, which motivated their study.
 87 However, they did not focus on the influence of the nebulizer resistance on the peak flow rate values
 88 during breathing. When breathing through a device with significant pressure drop, the patients may
 89 intuitively adjust the inspiration flow rate according to their abilities. The difference in the peak flow
 90 values may impact regional lung deposition more than the modelled shape.

91 This study first investigates whether the resistance of the nebulizer is significant enough to affect the
 92 patient’s breathing profile and, if so, what is its effect on aerosol regional lung deposition. A second task
 93 focuses on the effect of the slow and deep inhalation technique on flow rate profiles and its influence on
 94 regional aerosol deposition using a realistic lung replica and computational fluid dynamics.

95 *Table 1: List of commonly used nebulizers and their recommended inhalation technique according to the device instruction*
 96 *manual.*

	Inhalation instruction		
	Breath normally	Slow & deep inhalation	Other
Omron NE-C801 ¹⁹	✓		
Omron NE-C28 ²⁰	✓		
Pari eFlow Rapid ²¹		✓	
Pari LC Sprint ²²		✓	
Pari LC Sprint Star ²³		✓	
Aerogen ²⁴	✓		
Aeroeclipse ²⁵		✓	
Philips SideStreams ²⁶			Slowly breathe in and out.
MYNEB ²⁷	✓		
Philips InnoSpire Go ²⁸	✓		
MABISMist™ II ²⁹			Follow the instructions provided by your physician.
I-neb AAD system ³⁰	✓		

97

98

99 2 Methods

100 Flow resistance or pressure drop when using three types of nebulizers and their influence on the
101 inhalation profile and aerosol lung deposition were investigated in this study.

102 2.1 Pressure drop measurement

103 A jet nebulizer Pari LC Sprint Star (Pari GmbH, Starnberg, Germany) and two mesh nebulizers, Aerogen
104 Ultra (Aerogen Ltd., Galway, Ireland) and eFlowRapid (Pari GmbH, Starnberg, Germany), were used.
105 The nebulizers were connected to a vacuum pump (Busch R5 PA0008C, Busch Vacuum Solutions s.r.o
106 Czech Republic). For pressure drop characteristics, a pressure difference sensor Fluke 922 Airflow
107 Meter (Fluke Corp., Washington, USA) was connected according to the scheme in *Figure 1* – upstream
108 and downstream of the nebulizer. A flow meter TSI 4040 was connected between the pressure difference
109 measuring point and the vacuum pump. The pressure drop was measured for the expected range of flow
110 rates during the nebulizer usage – up to 40 l/min.

111 Since a spirometer SpiroSonic Smart (Uscom Ltd., Australia) and a mouthpiece were connected to the
112 nebulizers during the following measurements, their effect on the pressure drop was also measured.
113 Connecting the spirometer and its mouthpiece increased the pressure drop by 3.53 ± 2.16 % of its value
114 when measured only with the nebulizer.

115

116

117 *Figure 1: The scheme of the pressure drop measurement.*

118

119 2.2 Breathing profiles recording

120 Ten healthy male subjects were asked to breathe through the Pari LC Sprint Star, Aerogen Ultra, and
121 eFlow Rapid nebulizers. Only male subjects were selected because only male airway geometry was used
122 for the regional airway deposition investigation in the following part of the study. All the subjects were
123 informed about the content of the study and informed consent was signed. A study on female airways is
124 planned for the future. Elementary data about the subjects are shown in *Table 2*. The nebulizer was
125 connected to the spirometer outlet (SpiroSonic Smart, Uscom Ltd., Australia), and a mouthpiece was
126 connected to the other side. During the measurement, the patients wore nose clips to ensure breathing
127 through the mouth. They were asked to seal the lips around the mouthpiece properly. The subjects were
128 instructed to perform two different inhalation techniques: first, spontaneous normal breathing and

129 second, slow and deep breathing. As a reference case, breathing without a nebulizer was measured for
 130 inhalation techniques. The scheme of the breathing profile recording is shown in *Figure 2*.

131 *Table 2: Elementary data about investigated male subjects.*

	Age [y]	Weight [kg]	Height [cm]
<i>Sub1</i>	29	85	183
<i>Sub2</i>	40	76	179
<i>Sub3</i>	24	79	179
<i>Sub4</i>	31	80	189
<i>Sub5</i>	39	79	181
<i>Sub6</i>	35	93	193
<i>Sub7</i>	32	88	183
<i>Sub8</i>	27	114	204
<i>Sub9</i>	27	94	190
<i>Sub10</i>	28	65	177

132

133

134 *Figure 2: Scheme of the breathing profile measurement.*

135 **2.3 Breathing profiles analysis**

136 Flow rate as a function of time was recorded during the measurements. First, the inspirations and
 137 expirations were separated and divided into individual profiles (*Figure 3*). This division was performed
 138 according to the local extremes of the volume recording of breathing. Error samples and outliers (for
 139 example fluctuations, a cough, etc.) were manually discarded from the statistical group.

140

141 *Figure 3: The separation of individual inspiration and expiration.*

142 For the generalization and comparison between the regimes, the time was normalized in each inspiration
143 (expiration) by the total time of the inspiration (expiration). Then, the recorded inspiration (expiration)
144 flow profiles were normalized by the average inspiration flow rate in the non-nebulizer mode of the
145 investigated subject calculated as

$$146 \quad \bar{V}_i = \frac{TV}{T_i},$$

147 where TV is the tidal volume of the breathing, and T_i is the total time of inspiration. Such a normalization
148 enables comparing all the flow rate profiles.

149 Moreover, a simplified reconstruction of the breathing profile for a patient-specific case can be easily
150 performed by multiplying the normalized profile by the patient-specific \bar{V}_i value. Therefore, only two
151 parameters (TV , T_i) must be measured to reconstruct the real patient case. This can help in personalized
152 lung deposition predictions. The statistical analysis described below was performed on normalized
153 breathing profiles, as the normalization removed the effect of individual body size and lung volume.

154 **2.3.1 Statistical methods**

155 For statistical testing, the averages of normalized flow profiles were compared. The ANOVA could not
156 be applied since the normality assumption was not fulfilled for spontaneous and “slow and deep”
157 breathing. Therefore, a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was used³¹. The testing procedure involves
158 mixing all the data together, sorting them in ascending order, assigning them a rank and dividing them
159 into initial groups. The data is then divided back to the original groups, and the average rank for each
160 group is computed. The null hypothesis of the Kruskal-Wallis test is that all the ranks are the same, i.e.
161 the averages are similar. Subsequently, the Dunn-Sidak pair test was used to compare the nebulizers
162 pairwise.

163 **2.4 CFD breathing profile simulations**

164 A computational fluid mechanics tool Simcenter Star-CCM+ 2210 (Siemens Industry Software Inc.,
165 Texas, USA) was used to compare the flow rate profile effect on regional aerosol deposition in human
166 lung geometry.

167 **2.4.1 Airway geometry**

168 The airway geometry used for the computations is described in detail in³². The upper airways were
169 obtained from the Lovelace Respiratory Research Institute (LRRRI). The mouth cavity was moulded from
170 an *in vivo* dental impression of a Caucasian male, and the remaining part of the upper airways was
171 acquired as a cast from a cadaver³³. The conducting airways, in turn, were acquired from an adult male
172 lung post-autopsy. Subsequently, these airways were filled with a rubber solution and scanned by high-
173 resolution computational tomography (HRCT) after removal of lung tissue³⁴. This geometry was
174 processed to be 3D printable, therefore it was shortened to seven generations of branching, and the
175 channels of terminal bronchi were connected to ten outlets³⁵ (*Figure 4*). This model is available in open
176 access from the ERCOFTAC database³⁶.

177

Figure 4: Airway model used for CFD computations.

178
179

180 2.4.2 Flow field

181 Velocity boundary conditions were prescribed on the ten outlets of the geometry, while an atmospheric
182 pressure boundary was set at the inlet to the mouth cavity. The flow rate breathing profiles were
183 reconstructed from the normalized breathing profiles, shown in *Figure 8* and *Figure 10*, by determining
184 the average value of T_V and T_i of spontaneous breathing without a nebulizer. The reconstructed
185 breathing profiles were accordingly represented in *Figure 9* and *Figure 11* for spontaneous breathing
186 and slow and deep breathing, respectively. It should be noted that, due to the computational costs, only
187 the inspiration phase of the cycle was simulated in the airway deposition simulations.

188 The flow distribution between the lobes was determined based on the dynamic 4D-CT scanning data
189 reported by Jahani et al.³⁷. The flow distribution between the outlets of the geometry was set according
190 to the experimentally measured data reported by³⁸.

191 The unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (uRANS) approach with Menter's SST $k-\omega$ turbulence
192 model³⁹ was employed to model the turbulent behaviour in the system. The time step was set as
193 3×10^{-4} s to satisfy the Courant number < 5 condition. The maximum Courant number evaluated for the
194 extreme case of peak flow rate among the breathing cycles (total flow rate of 40.23 l/min - peak
195 inspiration flow rate of the regime without inhaler during the spontaneous breathing) was 4.1, which
196 was reached only in a few cells in the domain. The average Courant number was below 1, which
197 confirmed that the time step of 3×10^{-4} s was appropriate for the subsequent calculations.

198 2.4.3 Computational mesh

199 A computational mesh was created by the Star-CCM+ mesh generator and consisted of polyhedral
200 elements. A prismatic layer near the wall was generated to describe the behaviour in this area and was
201 composed of 10 layers. Five different meshes were generated with 3.8, 4.5, 5.6, 7.1, and 8.0 million
202 cells to assess mesh independence. The simulations for the mesh independency test used the uRANS
203 approach for the highest peak flow rate from all the investigated breathing regimes, with a total flow

204 rate of 40.23 l/min. The nine-point probes for the mesh independence evaluation were located along the
 205 laryngeal jet since more turbulent behaviour was expected in this area. The velocity magnitude was
 206 measured in these point probes. No significant difference between the results with the 7.1 and 8.0 million
 207 cell mesh occurred (*Figure 5*), therefore the 7.1 million cells were considered enough for the
 208 calculations.
 209

210
 211 *Figure 5: Velocity magnitude in the point probes calculated on selected meshes.*

212
 213 **2.4.4 Particle transport**

214 In this study, aerosol particles were introduced into a simulation domain via 100 evenly distributed point
 215 injectors at the mouth inlet, as illustrated in *Figure 6*. Each point injected one particle at a time step.
 216 Four particle sizes were set: 1 μm , 2.5 μm , 5 μm , and 10 μm . Upon contact with the wall, the particles
 217 were considered deposited, with no rebound accounted for. The particles were deemed to have been
 218 deposited when they were at a distance of half the particle diameter from the wall. Any particles that
 219 exited the simulation domain via the outlets were considered to have penetrated below the investigated
 220 section of the airways. The regional aerosol deposition was then determined by dividing the number of
 221 particles deposited in the investigated region by the total number of particles deposited in the whole
 222 domain or penetrated through the whole model.

223
 224 *Figure 6: Point injectors distribution.*

226 3 Results & Discussion

227 3.1 Nebulizer pressure drop

228 The pressure drop of the nebulizers was measured in a set of three measurements, and the error bars in
229 the plot (Figure 7) represent the standard deviation from this set.

230

231 Figure 7: Pressure drop of the nebulizers in dependence on inspiration flow rate.

232 The results showed that the pressure drop dependence on the flow rate was linear for both mesh
233 nebulizers, with Aerogen Ultra exhibiting a slightly higher pressure drop compared to eFlowRapid.
234 However, a significant difference was observed in the case of Pari LC Sprint Star, which contains a
235 silicone inspiration valve in the upper part of the nebulizer chamber. The valve closes at a flow rate of
236 approximately 20 l/min and is made of a flexible silicone material, which causes it to crumple when
237 closed. Due to its flexibility, the valve crumples into a different shape each time, leading to substantial
238 variability in the pressure drop at higher flow rates, as evidenced by the error bars in Figure 7.

239 3.2 Breathing profile analysis

240 3.2.1 Spontaneous breathing – inspiration

241 The breathing recordings were analysed to assess the effect of the nebulizer pressure drop on the
242 breathing flow profile. The null hypothesis of the Kruskal-Wallis test is that all the ranks are the same,
243 i.e. the averages are very similar. For all the following testing, the significance level α was chosen to be
244 0.05. The Kruskal-Wallis test p -value equal to $7.4 \cdot 10^{-99}$ is lower than α , thus rejecting the null hypothesis
245 and meaning that at least one group (nebulizer type) significantly differs from other groups. In the
246 following Table 3, the p -values for the pairwise comparison by the Dunn-Sidak test are written. The
247 significance level α of Dunn-Sidak pairwise testing was also chosen to be 0.05 and kept for all the
248 subsequent datasets described below. The normalized flow profiles are shown in Figure 8, where the
249 error area around the curves represents the standard deviation of normalized profiles.

250 The data from Table 3 confirm that the breathing profile across various nebulizers differs significantly
251 from one another, except for the combination of nebulizers Aerogen Ultra and eFlowRapid where the
252 p -value is over significance level α . This means that both mesh nebulizers induced similar effects on the
253 patient's breathing, and the breathing profile through these two devices was nearly the same. In the case
254 of inspiration, all of the investigated nebulizers significantly affected the breathing profile compared to
255 the regime without a nebulizer. The inspiration route of the flow differs significantly between the
256 investigated nebulizers due to their construction and design. The pressure drop characteristics of the Pari
257 LC Sprint Star air-jet nebulizer (Figure 7) cause flow rate limitation during breathing. At a flow rate of
258 approximately 20 l/min, the inspiration valve of an air-jet nebulizer closes, which results in lower flow

259 rate values in spontaneous breathing. No such behaviour occurs with mesh nebulizers due to their design.
 260 The expiration route is very similar for all the investigated devices. The airflow is exhaled through the
 261 exhalation valve on the nebulizer mouthpiece and does not pass through the nebulizer body. The design
 262 of the mouthpiece and the exhalation valve is very similar for all the investigated devices.

263 3.2.2 Spontaneous breathing – expiration

264 The p -value of the Kruskal-Wallis test equal to $1.9 \cdot 10^{-71}$ shows that at least one group significantly
 265 differs from others. The p -values of the Dunn-Sidak pairwise comparison test are shown in *Table 3*. The
 266 normalized flow profiles are shown in *Figure 8*. The flow rate in these charts is normalized by the
 267 average flow rate during the inspiration of the specific subject without a nebulizer, and the time is
 268 normalized by the total inspiration time.

269 These results show that the effect of the nebulizer pressure drop on the patient’s spontaneous expiration
 270 is significant. However, unlike with the inspiration, there is no significant difference between the
 271 investigated nebulizers during the expiration. This difference between the effect on inspiration and
 272 expiration profile is caused by different routes of the flow, as was mentioned above.

273 *Table 3: Dunn-Sidak test p -values for the pairwise comparison.*

	Inspiration	Expiration
Aerogen Ultra — eFlowRapid	0.0699	0.0232
Aerogen Ultra — Pari LC Sprint Star	0	0.4368
Aerogen Ultra— Without nebulizer	0	0
eflowRapid — Pari LC Sprint Star	0	0.8373
eflowRapid — Without nebulizer	0	0
Pari LC Sprint Star — Without nebulizer	0	0

274
275

276
277 *Figure 8: Normalized breathing profiles of spontaneous breathing regime.*

278 **3.2.3 Spontaneous breathing profiles for CFD boundary conditions**

279 Since the pressure drop of the nebulizer affects the breathing flow rate, it is expected that the TV and the
 280 inspiration or expiration times (T_i , T_e) will also change. These values are shown in *Table 4*. The
 281 variability in this table represents the standard deviation from the inter-subject comparison. The average
 282 coefficients of intrasubject variability and their standard deviation are shown in *Table 5*.

283 *Table 4: Inspiration and expiration times and tidal volume of spontaneous breathing.*

Nebulizer	T_i [s]	T_e [s]	TV [l]
Aerogen	2.42 ± 0.68	2.93 ± 0.85	0.81 ± 0.14
eFlowRapid	2.40 ± 0.53	2.83 ± 0.68	0.76 ± 0.15
Pari LC Sprint Star	2.87 ± 0.76	2.84 ± 0.86	0.77 ± 0.19
No nebulizer	1.83 ± 0.25	2.32 ± 0.50	0.98 ± 0.23

284

285 *Table 5: Mean coefficients of intrasubject variability for spontaneous breathing: C_{Var_TV} – Coefficient of intrasubject
 286 variability of TV ; C_{Var_Ti} – Coefficient of intrasubject variability of T_i ; C_{Var_Te} – Coefficient of intrasubject variability of T_e ;*

	C_{Var_TV}	C_{Var_Ti}	C_{Var_Te}
Aerogen	0.16 ± 0.04	0.13 ± 0.04	0.12 ± 0.03
eFlow Rapid	0.16 ± 0.04	0.13 ± 0.04	0.16 ± 0.06
Pari LC Sprint Star	0.15 ± 0.05	0.13 ± 0.05	0.13 ± 0.04
No nebulizer	0.17 ± 0.04	0.13 ± 0.05	0.12 ± 0.05

287 The average breathing cycles were reconstructed by multiplying the average normalized flow profile by
 288 the average inspiration flow rate of the regime without an inhaler (TV/T_i). The inspiration and expiration
 289 times were reconstructed by the inspiration and expiration times from *Table 4*. These data confirmed an
 290 intuitive behaviour when the patient prolonged the inspiration while breathing with a pressure drop of
 291 the nebulizer in order to inspire a sufficient volume of air. Only the inspiration phase of reconstructed
 292 breathing cycles was used for the CFD simulations. After acquiring the patient's T_i and TV values, such
 293 reconstruction is also possible for a specific patient case. The reconstructed breathing cycles are shown
 294 in *Figure 9*.

295
296

Figure 9: The entire reconstructed spontaneous breathing cycles.

297 3.2.4 Slow and deep breathing - inspiration

298 The normalized slow and deep breathing regimes are shown in *Figure 10*. As described in section 2.3,
299 the flow rates were normalized by the average flow rate of the spontaneous inspiration. The non-
300 parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was applied similarly as in previous cases. The p -value of the test 0.0012
301 refers to the fact that at least one nebulizer significantly differs from others. The p -values of the pairwise
302 comparison are shown in *Table 6*.

303 Compared to spontaneous breathing results, the mesh nebulizers did not influence the breathing
304 significantly, while the Pari LC Sprint Star nebulizer did. The average normalized breathing profiles are
305 plotted in *Figure 10*. The influence of Pari LC Sprint Star is also visible in this figure.

306

Table 6: P -values of the pairwise comparison of slow and deep inspirations.

	Inspiration	Expiration
Aerogen Ultra — eFlowRapid	0.9968	0.0226
Aerogen Ultra — Pari LC Sprint Star	0.0259	0.9611
Aerogen Ultra — Without nebulizer	0.9979	0.9103
eFlowRapid — Pari LC Sprint Star	0.0042	0.2249
eFlowRapid — Without nebulizer	1	0.2263
Pari LC Sprint Star — Without nebulizer	0.0033	1

307

308 3.2.5 Slow and deep breathing – expiration

309 The p -value of the Kruskal-Wallis test equal to 0.0294 implies that at least one group significantly differs
310 from the other. The p -values of the pairwise Dunn-Sidak test are shown in *Table 6*. Based on the p -

311 values, the only statistically significant difference is between the Aerogen and the eFlowRapid despite
 312 their overall averages being closer than the averages of the eFlowRapid and Pari LC, which can be seen
 313 in *Figure 10*. However, this result is difficult to explain physically, since the route of the exhaled air is
 314 similar in all investigated nebulizers and a similar pressure drop is expected. This effect may have been
 315 caused by a small number of observations and large variability.

316 The flow rate profile comparison is plotted in *Figure 10*. The error area around the curves represents the
 317 standard deviations. These intervals show considerable variability between the recordings, so comparing
 318 the effects of the different nebulizers is not appropriate. This variability is caused by two simple issues.
 319 First, since the breathing cycle of this regime took a significantly longer time, a significantly lower
 320 number of inspirations and expirations was recorded. Second, training is necessary when the patient is
 321 asked to perform a particular inhalation technique. Each subject understood the instructions to breathe
 322 slowly and deeply differently. The same variability may also occur in the actual inhalation drug
 323 administration, and training could help reduce it. In the context of this variability, most of the observed
 324 differences between the slow and deep regimes are insignificant. This issue illustrates the difficulties of
 325 patient compliance with the inhalation technique and instruction.

326 Although the tested subjects tried to breathe slowly, the inspiration flow rate did not decrease much
 327 compared to spontaneous breathing. Slow and deep breathing resulted in lower flow rates, but only when
 328 breathing without a nebulizer. The flow rates of the inspiration profile through the vibrating mesh
 329 nebulizers, and the case without a nebulizer were very similar. The systematic difference between the
 330 air jet nebulizer Pari LC Sprint Star and the other nebulizers was also observed in the inspiration phase
 331 of this regime.

332
 333 *Figure 10: Normalized slow and deep breathing profiles.*

334 3.2.6 The slow and deep breathing profiles for CFD boundary conditions

335 *Table 7: Inspiration and expiration times and slow and deep breathing tidal volume.*

Nebulizer	T_i [s]	T_e [s]	TV [l]
Aerogen	10.60 ± 4.34	13.30 ± 5.06	3.54 ± 1.01
eFlowRapid	10.20 ± 3.85	11.44 ± 5.03	3.75 ± 0.83
Pari LC Sprint Star	12.05 ± 3.70	11.25 ± 4.85	3.35 ± 1.05
Without nebulizer	8.88 ± 2.44	11.84 ± 4.41	3.55 ± 1.09

337 *Table 8: Coefficients of intra-subject variability for slow and deep breathing: C_{Var_TV} – Coefficient of intra-subject variability*
 338 *of TV; C_{Var_Ti} – Coefficient of intra-subject variability of T_i ; C_{Var_Te} – Coefficient of intra-subject variability of T_e ;*

	C_{Var_TV}	C_{Var_Ti}	C_{Var_Te}
Aerogen	0.12 ± 0.06	0.14 ± 0.05	0.13 ± 0.05
eFlow Rapid	0.09 ± 0.04	0.10 ± 0.05	0.12 ± 0.05
Pari LC Sprint Star	0.14 ± 0.06	0.15 ± 0.08	0.18 ± 0.09
Without nebulizer	0.12 ± 0.03	0.17 ± 0.06	0.18 ± 0.10

339 The average breathing cycle was reconstructed by the average flow rate of the regime without an inhaler
 340 and the inspiration and expiration times from *Table 7*. The inspiration phase of the reconstructed
 341 breathing cycles was used for CFD simulations. Such reconstruction can be performed from the data
 342 presented here for any arbitrary patient case after acquiring the patient's T_i and T_e values (for
 343 spontaneous breathing). The reconstructed breathing cycles are shown in *Figure 11*.

344

345

Figure 11: Entire reconstructed slow and deep breathing cycles

346 3.3 Airways deposition

347 3.3.1 Spontaneous breathing

348 The results showed minimal differences in aerosol deposition of particles with sizes of 1 and 2.5 μm
 349 among the investigated nebulizers (*Figure 12*). Using nebulizers had only a slight effect on the
 350 deposition pattern of these particles compared to spontaneous breathing without a nebulizer. The
 351 difference in the regional deposition pattern of small particles may increase in deeper airways (below
 352 the seventh generation), which were not included in this study. In the case of particles with sizes of 5 and
 353 10 μm , a significantly higher number of particles can penetrate below the seven generations of branching
 354 when breathing through a nebulizer. The most significant fraction of the aerosol penetrating below the
 355 seventh branching generation was found in the case of the Pari LC Sprint Star air-jet nebulizer (*Figure*

356 12). This nebulizer had the highest pressure drop, which directly decreased the peak flow rates of the
357 inspiration.

358 Only the inspiration part of the cycle was simulated in this study. Therefore, an unknown portion of
359 particles penetrating below the replica is expected to be exhaled in a real administration. The deposition
360 during the exhalation phase of the measured breathing profiles can be the next step of this research.
361 Although it is commonly expected that a larger portion of particles with sizes larger than 5 μm would
362 deposit in the upper airways⁴⁰, only a small fraction of the aerosol is deposited there.

363 The specificity of the upper airway geometry also affects the upper airway deposition. Although the
364 airways used for this study are realistic and were acquired from a real human body, the laryngeal area
365 is relatively broad. This may result in minor upper airway deposition measured in this airway model
366 compared to models with narrower glottis. This fact was already measured in other studies using the
367 same geometry^{41,42}. Nonetheless, this geometry was validated with the *in vivo* data within study⁴³ as a
368 model for upper airway deposition investigation.

369

370 Figure 12: Aerosol regional deposition in the stages of the airway during spontaneous breathing through the nebulizers. ET -
371 Extrathoracic; Below - a fraction of the particles able to penetrate deeper.

372 These findings are crucial in terms of computational benefits for a personalized medicine approach. The
373 influence of the pressure drop of the selected nebulizer and the breathing profile is significant in terms
374 of aerosol deposition in the lungs and it should be taken into account when modelling drug delivery.
375 The breathing flow profile may also affect the particle size of the generated aerosol, according to Hu et
376 al.⁹.

377 3.3.2 Slow and deep breathing

378 In principle, slow and deep breathing during inhalation can facilitate the penetration of aerosol particles
379 deep into the lungs owing to a larger inhaled volume per breath. The instruction to adopt a slow breathing

380 technique can also induce patients to perform inspiration at lower flow rates. The effect of these
 381 instructions is shown in section 3.2.2. Although the breathing profiles reconstructed from the average
 382 case (*Figure 11*) were employed as boundary conditions for the aerosol deposition simulations, such
 383 conditions are associated with considerable uncertainty due to the large variability of the slow and deep
 384 breathing recordings.

385 The average flow rate profiles of inspiration without a nebulizer and through a mesh nebulizer were
 386 found to be quite similar. This is likely due to the lower effect of mesh nebulizer pressure drop at lower
 387 flow rates, and inter-subject variability could further diminish the importance of differences between
 388 cases. Consequently, the differences in the regional deposition were minimal due to this effect. Since
 389 flow rates of the breathing profile through the Pari LC Sprint Star nebulizer were again lower, similarly
 390 as in the case of spontaneous breathing, the fraction of the aerosol which penetrated deeper to the lungs
 391 with Pari LC Sprint Star, was the highest also for the slow and deep breathing regime.

392

393

394 *Figure 13: The regional aerosol deposition results after the slow, deep inhalation through the investigated nebulizers. ET -*
 395 *Extrathoracic; below - a fraction of the particles able to penetrate deeper.*

396 The difference between the regional deposition of 1 and 2.5 µm particles during slow and deep breathing
 397 is minor and does not significantly differ from spontaneous breathing. However, in the case of 5 µm and
 398 10 µm particles, the difference was considerable. The slow and deep inhalation technique resulted in a
 399 significant increase in the fraction of particles penetrating below the replica, particularly when breathing
 400 without a nebulizer. Specifically, the fraction of 5µm particles penetrating deeper increased by 16.4 %,
 401 and that of 10µm particles increased by 17.4 % compared to spontaneous breathing. Regarding breathing
 402 through a nebulizer, the most remarkable difference between slow and deep inhalation and spontaneous

403 breathing was observed in the case of the Pari LC Sprint Star nebulizer and 10 μ m particle size, where
404 the fraction of particles penetrating deeper increased by 7.6 %. This was also the only case where the
405 difference in the breathing profile through the nebulizer compared with the breathing without the
406 nebulizer was statistically significant (see section 3.2.4). In all other cases, the difference in the
407 deposition fraction caused by different inhalation techniques was less than 5 %. Although 5 % of the
408 inhaled drug mass is not negligible, this difference is probably not very significant from the perspective
409 of the high variability of slow and deep breathing (*Figure 10*) and in the context of the influence of
410 individual patients.

411 **4 Conclusions**

412 The pressure drops of the nebulizers caused a decrease in the flow rates during breathing, with this effect
413 being the most significant with the Pari LC Sprint Star nebulizer due to the device's design and
414 construction. Lower breathing flow rates help to deliver therapeutic aerosol deeper into the lungs. Hence,
415 among the tested devices, the Pari LC Sprint Star air jet nebulizer appears to be the most suitable for
416 this purpose.

417 The key findings of this paper are: First, the pressure drop caused by the nebulizer device may
418 significantly affect the flow rate profile of a patient's breathing; second, this effect varies between the
419 nebulizers according to their design or principle; third, this effect influences the aerosol deposition in
420 human airways mainly in the case of larger particles (a significant effect on smaller particles was not
421 observed within the scope of seven generations of branching, but it may gain importance in the lower
422 parts of the respiratory tract); fourth, slow and deep inhalation technique may make the patients breathe
423 with lower flow rates, which would result in a higher fraction of particles able to penetrate deeper to the
424 lungs (this influences mainly larger particles) but the patient's adherence to the inhalation technique
425 rapidly increases the variability. These findings may be necessary in the field of personalized medicine
426 or a digital twin approach for a treatment design, as these differences need to be considered when
427 predicting aerosol deposition.

428 The significant limitation of this study is that only one specific airway geometry was used for the
429 investigation. The observed variations of the breathing profiles are expected to have a different influence
430 on regional lung deposition due to the morphometric specificity of the airways.

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434 **6 CRediT authorship contribution statement**

435 **Ondrej Mišík:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing
436 – Original draft, Visualization. **František Prinz:** Data curation, Formal analysis. **Jakub Elcner:**
437 Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Matouš Cabalka:** Data curation, Formal analysis. **Miloslav**
438 **Bělka:** Writing – review & editing. **František Lízal:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project
439 administration, Funding acquisition.

440 **7 Declaration of interests**

441 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that
442 could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

443 **8 Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies**
444 **in the writing process**

445 During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used AI Writing Assistance of Grammarly in order to
446 correct and revise the language and grammar. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and
447 edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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453 **9 References**

- 454 1. Kaul H. Respiratory Healthcare by Design: Computational Approaches Bringing Respiratory
455 Precision and Personalised Medicine Closer to Bedside. *Morphologie* 2019;103(343):194–202;
456 doi: 10.1016/j.morpho.2019.10.042.
- 457 2. Farkas Á, Tomisa G, Szénási G, et al. The Effect of Lung Emptying before the Inhalation of
458 Aerosol Drugs on Drug Deposition in the Respiratory System. *Int J Pharm X* 2023;6(May); doi:
459 10.1016/j.ijpx.2023.100192.
- 460 3. Farkas Á, Tomisa G, Kugler S, et al. The Effect of Exhalation before the Inhalation of Dry
461 Powder Aerosol Drugs on the Breathing Parameters, Emitted Doses and Aerosol Size
462 Distributions. *Int J Pharm X* 2023;5(February); doi: 10.1016/j.ijpx.2023.100167.
- 463 4. Ye Y, Fan Z, Ma Y, et al. Investigation on the Influence of Design Features on the Performance
464 of Dry Powder Inhalers: Spiral Channel, Mouthpiece Dimension, and Gas Inlet. *Int J Pharm*
465 2023;642(January):123116; doi: 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2023.123116.
- 466 5. Roth AP, Lange CF and Finlay WH. The Effect of Breathing Pattern on Nebulizer Drug Delivery.
467 *J Aerosol Med Depos Clear Eff Lung* 2003;16(3):325–339; doi: 10.1089/089426803769017677.
- 468 6. Hickey AJ. *Pharmaceutical Inhalation Aerosol Technology*. Crc Press; 2019.
- 469 7. Pritchard JN, Hatley RH, Denyer J, et al. Mesh Nebulizers Have Become the First Choice for
470 New Nebulized Pharmaceutical Drug Developments. *Ther Deliv* 2018;9(2):121–136; doi:
471 10.4155/tde-2017-0102.
- 472 8. Ari A. Jet, Ultrasonic, and Mesh Nebulizers: An Evaluation of Nebulizers for Better Clinical
473 Outcomes. *Eurasian J Pulmonol* 2014;16(1):1–7; doi: 10.5152/ejp.2014.00087.
- 474 9. Hu J, Zhang R, Beng H, et al. Effects of Flow Pattern, Device and Formulation on Particle Size
475 Distribution of Nebulized Aerosol. *Int J Pharm* 2019;560(January):35–46; doi:
476 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2019.01.025.
- 477 10. Nerbrink O. Nebulizers: Past to Present Platforms and Future Possibilities. *Inhalation* 2016;10:1–
478 6.
- 479 11. Dolovich MB and Dhand R. Aerosol Drug Delivery: Developments in Device Design and
480 Clinical Use. *Lancet* 2011;377(9770):1032–1045; doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(10)60926-9.
- 481 12. Taffet GE, Donohue JF and Altman PR. Clinical Interventions in Aging Dovepress
482 Considerations for Managing Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease in the Elderly. *Clin Interv*
483 *Aging* 2014;9:23–30.
- 484 13. Hosseini S and Golshahi L. An in Vitro Evaluation of Importance of Airway Anatomy in Sub-
485 Regional Nasal and Paranasal Drug Delivery with Nebulizers Using Three Different Anatomical
486 Nasal Airway Replicas of 2-, 5- and 50-Year Old Human Subjects. *Int J Pharm*
487 2019;563(April):426–436; doi: 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2019.04.019.
- 488 14. Riedler J and Robertson CF. Effect of Tidal Volume on the Output and Particle Size Distribution
489 of Hypertonic Saline from an Ultrasonic Nebulizer. *Eur Respir J* 1994;7(5):998–1002; doi:
490 10.1183/09031936.94.07050998.
- 491 15. Ari A. Effect of Nebulizer Type, Delivery Interface, and Flow Rate on Aerosol Drug Delivery
492 to Spontaneously Breathing Pediatric and Infant Lung Models. *Pediatr Pulmonol*
493 2019;54(11):1735–1741; doi: 10.1002/ppul.24449.
- 494 16. Finlay WH. *The Mechanics of Inhaled Pharmaceutical Aerosols*. Academic Press; 2001.

- 495 17. Zhao X and Yu X. Expert Consensus on Nebulization Therapy in Pre-Hospital and in-Hospital
496 Emergency Care. *Ann Transl Med* 2019;7(18):487–487; doi: 10.21037/atm.2019.09.44.
- 497 18. Ari A. Jet, Ultrasonic, and Mesh Nebulizers: An Evaluation of Nebulizers for Better Clinical
498 Outcomes. *Eurasian J Pulmonol* 2014;16(1):1–7; doi: 10.5152/ejp.2014.00087.
- 499 19. Omron Healthcare. Instruction Manual: Compressor Nebulizer NE-C801. 2011.
- 500 20. Omron Healthcare. Instruction Manual: Compressor Nebulizer MODEL NE-C28. 2006.
- 501 21. PARI Pharma. EFlow Rapid Nebulizer System: Instruction for Use. 2022.
- 502 22. Ltd PM. User Guide: Nebulising with the Pari LC Sprint. n.d.
- 503 23. PARI Pharma. Instruction for Use: Pari LC Sprint Star. 2021.
- 504 24. Aerogen Ltd. Aerogen Solo: System Instruction Manual. 2020.
- 505 25. Trudell Medical International. AeroEclipse XL: BAN Nebulizer. 2022.
- 506 26. Philips Respironics. SideStream Nebulizers: How to Use Your SideStream Nebulizer. 2014.
- 507 27. 3A HEALTH CARE S.r.l. MYNEB: Instruction Manual. 2018.
- 508 28. DirectHome Medical. How to Use Your Philips InnoSpire Go. n.d.
- 509 29. MABIS HEALTHCARE INC. MABISMist™ II Ultrasonic Nebulizer Guidebook. 2002.
- 510 30. Philips Respironics. I-Neb AAD System: User Guide. 2015.
- 511 31. Kruskal WH and Wallis WA. Use of Ranks in One-Criterion Variance Analysis. *J Am Stat Assoc*
512 1952;47(260):583–621; doi: 10.1080/01621459.1952.10483441.
- 513 32. Lizal F, Elcner J, Hopke PK, et al. Development of a Realistic Human Airway Model. *Proc Inst*
514 *Mech Eng Part H J Eng Med* 2012;226(3):197–207; doi: 10.1177/0954411911430188.
- 515 33. Cheng KH, Cheng YS, Yeh HC, et al. An Experimental Method for Measuring Aerosol
516 Deposition Efficiency in the Human Oral Airway. *Am Ind Hyg Assoc J* 1997;58(3):207–213;
517 doi: 10.1080/15428119791012856.
- 518 34. Schmidt A, Zidowitz S, Kriete A, et al. A Digital Reference Model of the Human Bronchial Tree.
519 *Comput Med Imaging Graph* 2004;28(4):203–211; doi: 10.1016/j.compmedimag.2004.01.001.
- 520 35. Koullapis P, Kassinos SC, Muela J, et al. Regional Aerosol Deposition in the Human Airways:
521 The SimInhale Benchmark Case and a Critical Assessment of in Silico Methods. *Eur J Pharm*
522 *Sci* 2018;113(June 2017):77–94; doi: 10.1016/j.ejps.2017.09.003.
- 523 36. Koullapis P, Lizal F, Jedelsky J, et al. Ercoftac: Biomedical Flows. n.d. Available from:
524 https://kbwiki.ercoftac.org/w/index.php/Biomedical_Flows.
- 525 37. Jahani N, Choi S, Choi J, et al. Assessment of Regional Ventilation and Deformation Using 4D-
526 CT Imaging for Healthy Human Lungs during Tidal Breathing. *J Appl Physiol*
527 2015;119(10):1064–1074; doi: 10.1152/jappphysiol.00339.2015.
- 528 38. Farkas Á, Lizal F, Jedelsky J, et al. The Role of the Combined Use of Experimental and
529 Computational Methods in Revealing the Differences between the Micron-Size Particle
530 Deposition Patterns in Healthy and Asthmatic Subjects. *J Aerosol Sci* 2020;147(April):1–16;
531 doi: 10.1016/j.jaerosci.2020.105582.
- 532 39. Menter FR. Two-Equation Eddy-Viscosity Turbulence Models for Engineering Applications.
533 *AIAA J* 1994;32(8):1598–1605; doi: 10.2514/3.12149.
- 534 40. Cheng YS. Mechanisms of Pharmaceutical Aerosol Deposition in the Respiratory Tract. *AAPS*

- 535 PharmSciTech 2014;15(3):630–640; doi: 10.1208/s12249-014-0092-0.
- 536 41. Szabová J, Mišík O, Fučík J, et al. Liposomal Form of Erlotinib for Local Inhalation
537 Administration and Efficiency of Its Transport to the Lungs. *Int J Pharm* 2023;634(November
538 2022); doi: 10.1016/j.ijpharm.2023.122695.
- 539 42. Lizal F, Elcner J, Jedelsky J, et al. The Effect of Oral and Nasal Breathing on the Deposition of
540 Inhaled Particles in Upper and Tracheobronchial Airways. *J Aerosol Sci* 2020;150(April); doi:
541 10.1016/j.jaerosci.2020.105649.
- 542 43. Cheng YS, Zhou Y and Chen BT. Particle Deposition in a Cast of Human Oral Airways. *Aerosol*
543 *Sci Technol* 1999;31(4):286–300; doi: 10.1080/027868299304165.
- 544

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